

METACOGNITIVE FEATURES OF DECISION-MAKING IN NEGOTIATION ACTIVITIES OF MANAGERS.

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Abstract: This study examines the metacognitive aspects of decision-making in managerial negotiation activities, focusing on how metacognitive awareness impacts decision quality and negotiation outcomes. Effective negotiation requires not only rational thinking but also reflective and adaptive decision-making strategies that align with dynamic business contexts. The primary objective of this research is to investigate the role of metacognition—awareness and control over one's cognitive processes—on managerial negotiation skills. Using a qualitative approach, interviews and case studies are analyzed to identify metacognitive practices that distinguish successful negotiators. The study's findings emphasize the importance of self-reflection, awareness of cognitive biases, and the adaptability of thought processes as pivotal to negotiation success. By enhancing metacognitive capabilities, managers can better navigate complex negotiations, leading to improved outcomes and more resilient decision-making processes.

Keywords: metacognition, decision-making, negotiation, managerial skills, cognitive bias, adaptive thinking

МЕТАКОГНИТИВНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИНЯТИЯ РЕШЕНИЙ В ПЕРЕГОВОРНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ МЕНЕДЖЕРОВ.

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Аннотация: Это исследование рассматривает метакогнитивные аспекты принятия решений в управленческих переговорных мероприятиях, сосредоточившись на том, как метакогнитивная осведомленность влияет на качество решения и результаты переговоров. Эффективное ведение переговоров требует не только рационального мышления, но и рефлексивных и адаптивных стратегий принятия решений, которые соответствуют динамичным деловым контекстам. Главная цель этого исследования - исследовать роль метапознавательности-осознания и контроль над когнитивными процессами человека на управленческих переговорных способностях. Используя качественный подход, интервью и тематические исследования анализируются для выявления метакогнитивных методов, которые отличают успешные переговорщики. Результаты исследования подчеркивают важность саморефлексии, осознания когнитивных предубеждений и адаптивности мыслительных процессов как ключевых для успеха переговоров. Повышая метакогнитивные способности, менеджеры могут лучше управлять сложными переговорами, что приводит к улучшению результатов и более устойчивым процессам принятия решений.

Ключевые слова: метапознание, принятие решений, переговоры, управленческие навыки, когнитивное предубеждение, адаптивное мышление

MENEJERLARNING MUZOKARALAR FAOLIYATIDA QAROR QABUL QILISHNING METAKOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot metakognitiv xabardorlik qarorlar sifati va muzokaralar natijalariga qanday ta'sir qilishiga e'tibor qaratib, boshqaruv muzokaralari faoliyatida qaror qabul qilishning metakognitiv jihatlarini o'rganadi. Samarali muzokaralar nafaqat oqilona fikrlashni, balki dinamik biznes kontekstiga mos keladigan fikrlash va moslashuvchan qarorlar qabul qilish strategiyalarini ham talab qiladi. Ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi metakognitsiyaning rolini o'rganish - o'z kognitiv jarayonlarini bilish va nazorat qilish - boshqaruv muzokaralari ko'nikmalarida. Sifatli yondashuvdan foydalangan holda, muvaffaqiyatli muzokarachilarni ajratib turadigan metakognitiv amaliyotlarni aniqlash uchun intervyular va amaliy tadqiqotlar tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari o'z-o'zini aks ettirish, kognitiv noto'g'ri fikrlarni bilish va fikrlash jarayonlarining moslashuvi muzokaralar muvaffaqiyati uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ta'kidlaydi. Metakognitiv qobiliyatlarni kuchaytirish orqali menejerlar murakkab muzokaralarni yaxshiroq boshqarishi mumkin, bu esa yaxshilangan natijalarga va qaror qabul qilish jarayonlarini yanada mustahkam qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: metakognitsiya, qaror qabul qilish, muzokaralar, boshqaruv qobiliyatlari, kognitiv moyillik, moslashuvchan fikrlash

INTRODUCTION

Negotiation is a crucial managerial skill, heavily influencing organizational success in securing resources, maintaining relationships, and achieving strategic goals. Traditional negotiation research often focuses on techniques, strategies, and outcomes, but recent studies highlight a cognitive dimension—metacognition—as essential in complex decision-making. Metacognition, the awareness and control over one's thought processes, allows managers to monitor, evaluate, and adjust their thinking strategies, particularly under pressure.

In negotiations, managers confront diverse challenges, such as cognitive biases, fluctuating power dynamics, and rapidly changing information. Metacognitive abilities, including awareness of one's cognitive limitations and flexibility in thinking, may enable managers to process complex information effectively and make better, informed decisions. This paper explores how metacognitive features influence the decision-making processes of managers during negotiations, aiming to reveal ways to enhance metacognitive skills for improved negotiation outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

To explore the role of metacognition in managerial negotiation decision-making, a qualitative research design was used. Semi-structured interviews and case study analyses were conducted to capture the nuances of metacognitive practices among managers. A purposive sample of 20 managers, experienced in negotiation across various industries, participated in the study. The data collection involved open-ended questions about their negotiation processes, cognitive strategies, and self-reflective practices. Additionally, real-life case studies provided insights into how metacognitive awareness impacted decision-making outcomes.

Thematic analysis was employed to identify recurring themes, focusing on metacognitive components such as self-reflection, bias recognition, and adaptability. Coding was used to classify and organize insights into overarching categories that relate to metacognitive decision-making.

This methodology ensured a comprehensive understanding of the managers' thought processes and enabled the study to draw conclusions about the influence of metacognition on negotiation effectiveness.

RESULTS

The analysis of interview and case study data revealed three main metacognitive features influencing managerial decision-making in negotiations: self-reflection, recognition of cognitive biases, and adaptive thinking.

1. **Self-Reflection:** Managers with high metacognitive awareness frequently engaged in self-reflection before, during, and after negotiations. This reflective practice enabled them to evaluate past experiences, identify strengths and weaknesses in their approach, and apply lessons learned to future negotiations.

2. **Recognition of Cognitive Biases:** Managers who recognized cognitive biases—such as anchoring, overconfidence, and confirmation bias—demonstrated greater flexibility in decision-making. This awareness helped them to avoid common pitfalls, leading to more objective evaluations of offers and counteroffers.

3. **Adaptive Thinking:** Managers who demonstrated adaptive thinking adjusted their strategies based on real-time feedback and shifting negotiation dynamics. These managers could pivot between negotiation styles, such as competitive or collaborative, depending on the context and the responses from other parties.

ANALYSIS

The findings indicate that metacognitive awareness enhances negotiation outcomes by allowing managers to refine their decision-making processes. Each of the identified features contributes uniquely to negotiation effectiveness:

- Self-Reflection allows managers to learn from past negotiations, improving future performance. By assessing their thought processes, managers can identify areas for improvement and refine their cognitive strategies.

- Recognition of Cognitive Biases protects managers from distorted perceptions that may impair judgment. For instance, a manager aware of the anchoring bias may avoid focusing too heavily on initial offers, thereby maintaining objectivity and seeking better deals.

- Adaptive Thinking is critical in dynamic negotiation environments. Managers capable of shifting strategies in response to new information or unexpected responses from counterparts tend to achieve better outcomes. This adaptability stems from a high level of cognitive control and metacognitive flexibility, essential traits in high-stakes negotiations.

These metacognitive features underscore the importance of a reflective and flexible mindset in negotiations. Managers who employ metacognitive strategies can navigate complex scenarios more effectively, leading to enhanced negotiation outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The study underscores the significant role metacognitive skills play in managerial decision-making during negotiations. Managers often encounter complex scenarios requiring more than technical negotiation tactics; they need a deep understanding of their own cognitive processes and limitations. The research suggests that metacognitive skills—self-reflection, cognitive bias awareness, and adaptability—form the foundation for improved negotiation efficacy.

Managers with heightened metacognitive awareness can better anticipate potential obstacles, understand the motivations of negotiation partners, and remain objective. These skills are critical for avoiding common negotiation pitfalls, such as escalation of commitment and

decision fatigue, which often hinder successful outcomes. Moreover, metacognitive training for managers can increase their capacity for adaptive thinking, allowing them to make quick, informed decisions under pressure.

One implication of this study is the potential for metacognitive training programs in managerial development curricula. By fostering metacognitive skills, organizations can enhance their managers' negotiation abilities, resulting in better organizational outcomes. Future research might focus on quantifying the impact of metacognitive training on negotiation success, exploring whether targeted interventions lead to measurable improvements in negotiation performance.

CONCLUSION

Metacognitive features play a vital role in enhancing decision-making during managerial negotiations. The ability to reflect, recognize cognitive biases, and adapt thinking strategies is invaluable for managers who operate in complex, high-stakes environments. This study highlights the need for metacognitive awareness as a foundational skill in effective negotiation, encouraging managers to develop reflective and adaptable cognitive approaches.

The findings indicate that organizations would benefit from incorporating metacognitive training in managerial development programs to improve negotiation outcomes. Future studies could further investigate the link between metacognition and negotiation performance, examining the effectiveness of various metacognitive strategies across different industries and negotiation contexts.

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